

RESTORATION OF FERTILITY AFTER SURGERY TO REMOVE UTERINE FIBROIDS IN PATIENTS OF THE OLDER REPRODUCTIVE GROUP.

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Relevance. Myomectomy is a method of choice in women of reproductive age. Despite significant research, this literature data is contradictory regarding the indications and contraindications for this operation, as well as the operative approach and technique of the operation [2, 8, 7]. At the same time, the effectiveness of infertility treatment largely depends on the condition of the ovarian reserve in each specific case. In the last decade, the concept of "ovarian reserve" and its significance in choosing infertility treatment methods have been widely discussed [3, 6, 15]. It is one of the most common diseases in women, reaching 12-25% of all gynecological diseases. The highest incidence of uterine fibroids occurs during the late reproductive period and before menopause. There is an opinion that the true prevalence of myoma is significantly higher and exceeds 70% both in Russia and abroad.

Purpose. Study of the significance of the myomectomy method for the implementation of reproductive function in the presence of single myomatous nodes that do not damage the uterine cavity.

Research material and methods. In order to analyze the effectiveness of myomectomy in relation to the restoration of fertility in older women of reproductive age, for whom infertility was the main indication for surgical intervention, a clinical and statistical analysis of the long-term results of the operation was conducted.

Discussion of results. By analyzing the frequency of pregnancy in patients with uterine fibroids (UF) of older reproductive age with reduced and low ovarian reserve (OR), the following conclusions can be drawn.

With reduced ovarian reserve, pregnancy occurred in 3 out of 7 patients (14.2%). In patients with low ovarian reserve, independent pregnancy after ovulation stimulation was not recorded. The use of assisted reproductive technologies (ART) - extracorporeal fertilization (ECO) allowed achieving pregnancy in 1 out of 11 patients (5.2%).

Thus, when establishing an initially reduced ovarian reserve, the patient should be informed of a more pronounced disruption of the morphofunctional state of the ovaries after myomectomy and, as a consequence, possible failure in the implementation of reproductive function. With initially low ovarian reserve after myomectomy, reproductive function can only be achieved through IVF. If there is no need to perform it, if the patient wishes, it is advisable to perform myomectomy only for organ-preserving purposes.

Literature:

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